

Fuel-Performance-informed Neutronic Calculations for the European Sodium Fast Reactor with Metallic Fuel

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ABSTRACT

In the context of the EURATOM project ESFR-SIMPLE, a metallic-fueled version of the European Sodium Fast Reactor is being studied (ESFR-M), targeting neutronics, fuel performance and safety analysis. For the neutronic simulation of the ESFR-M, nominal burnup-independent assumptions are normally used to account for phenomena such as fuel swelling and sodium infiltration. Specifically, the fuel is assumed to be fully-swollen from the beginning of the irradiation and 30% of the sodium originally located in the fuel-cladding gap is assumed to have infiltrated in the fuel porosity. In this work, fuel-performance-informed neutronic calculations are carried out, in order to account for the evolution of fuel properties during irradiation. The information from reference SAS4A/SASSYS-1 fuel performance simulations is transferred to burnup calculation in the Monte-Carlo code Serpent2. The results in terms of once-through and multi-batch core reactivity evolution are analyzed, yielding a maximum reactivity difference along the irradiation of around 200 pcm with respect to the reference simulations. While confirming the validity of the reference modeling assumptions, the developed methodology is found to be useful as a detailed analysis tool. Specifically, it allows to assess the potential impact of the uncertainty on fuel properties inputs on ESFR neutronic calculations. Future work will aim at extending this methodology to fission gas release and cladding strain.

Keywords: Sodium Fast Reactors, Metallic Fuel, Fuel Performance, Neutronics

1. INTRODUCTION

Metallic fuel is the reference option in the USA for Sodium Fast Reactors (SFR) according to a vast operational experience as well as several research initiatives. On the other hand, oxide fuel has been the selected option for several European countries in the frame of previous research projects [1, 2]. The ESFR-SIMPLE project [3], as the latest European iteration on the SFR design and safety assessment, includes among its main goals the development and evaluation of a modified version of the European Sodium Fast Reactor (ESFR) based on metallic fuel.

Metallic and oxide fuel types differ in their properties, such as density or thermal conductivity, and provide the reactor core with a unique set of responses to operational transients. Activities carried out in the ESFR-SIMPLE project aim at delivering a thorough comparison concerning the benefits and limitations of these two fuel types for the same reactor design. Naturally, this comparison should rely on the joint feedback from neutronics, fuel performance and safety analysis computational tools.

As first step, a detailed review of past experience in metallic fuel for SFRs was carried out with the goal of selecting main designing parameters [4]. Special emphasis was placed on the irradiation performance of selected metallic fuels so that the ESFR with metallic fuel (ESFR-M) design benefits from the main outcomes of that review. Subsequently, a core design study was conducted based on the design parameters previously selected [5]. As a result of that study, a first version of the ESFR-M design was

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delivered, rigorously meeting the main recommendation for metallic-fueled SFRs to provide essential input for further safety analyses.

Metallic fuel behaves quite differently compared to oxide fuel so that a dedicated fuel performance analysis has been carried out in order to support the ESFR-M design choices [6]. The analysis highlighted the phenomena that play a key role when metallic fuel is under irradiation. In accordance with the available literature on metallic-fueled cores, two crucial effects, with potential impact on the neutronics performance of the reactor, were identified: fuel axial elongation and in-pin sodium relocation. This paper evaluates the impact of the burnup-dependent fuel axial expansion and sodium bond relocation on the core performance via a dynamic update of the neutronics calculations.

2. THE ESFR-M CORE DESIGN AND REFERENCE RESULTS

The ESFR-M design is the metallic-fueled version of the ESFR concept. Annular MOX fuel with helium gap and ODS cladding is replaced by a sodium-bonded metallic fuel pin with HT9 cladding [5]. The radial core map is shown in Figure 1 and features two core zones: inner (IF) and outer (OF) fuel. Both zones are divided into six batches, retaining the same batch reloading scheme adopted for the ESFR-MOX, aiming at smoother reactivity variation and power peaking factors between batches [7]. Reactivity is controlled by 24 control and shutdown devices (CSD) and 12 diverse and shutdown devices (DSD). 31 corium discharge tubes (CDT) were retained from the original ESFR design with oxide fuel. The reduction of assembly flat-to-flat distance with respect to the ESFR-MOX design, allows extra spent fuel to be located in the core: three radial rings of spent fuel assemblies are located at the core boundary

Figure 1. ESFR-M radial layout.

From bottom to top axially, both inner and outer fuel feature a lower plug, a steel blanket, a fissile region, a gas plenum and an upper plug. The overall pin bundle height is the same in the two radial zones, however the outer fuel features a longer fissile height (“pancake” core) as shown in Figure 2. A sodium plenum is retained on top of the fuel bundle, together with a shielding region consisting of natural boron carbide (B4C) and stainless steel (EM10).

The designing phase demonstrated the optimal performance of the ESFR-M core concept. Compared to the ESFR-MOX, a reduced plutonium content was selected for the ESFR-M core. Reference core irradiation results are provided in [5] for once-through and multi-batch burnup calculations. On one hand, once-through calculations are performed for a total of 2100 effective full power days (EFPD), without reloading or reshuffling. Along the irradiation time, all control devices are withdrawn to their parking position. Regarding the computational approach, calculations are performed by means of the Monte Carlo code Serpent2.2 [8] and based on the continuous-energy JEFF-3.1 nuclear data library [9]. Fissile fuel regions are axially sub-divided into 5 burnable regions to account for different neutron flux

Figure 2. Axial description of the ESRF-M core sub-assemblies (length in mm and subscripts indicate the material ID), from top to bottom: inner fuel, outer fuel, corium discharge tube, CSD, DSD, radial reflectors R1/R2, and radial reflector R3.

Figure 3. On the left: ESRF-M core reactivity evolution as a function of irradiation time at nominal conditions (no fuel swelling) and with selected reference assumptions (fuel swelling modeling). On the right: ESRF-M cycle-wise core reactivity evolution for 3 consecutive full in-core residence periods using reference fuel swelling assumptions.

exposures while, radially, the batch-wise discretization with 6 burnable regions in inner and outer core is applied. Thus, fuel composition is independently tracked in a total of 60 burnable regions.

The burnup-dependent core reactivity evolution for the described ESRF-M configuration is depicted in Figure 3 (left). At nominal conditions, a reactivity of around 300 pcm is obtained at Beginning of Life (BOL), which is rapidly increasing along the irradiation reaching 1460 pcm after 1000 irradiation days. Then, it slowly decreases until the end of the considered irradiation time. As stated in [5], this behavior is explained due to the enhanced internal plutonium breeding resulting from the harder neutron spectrum and denser fuel, in comparison with the ESRF-MOX core.

Under nominal conditions, both fuel swelling and sodium bond infiltration are not considered, and the most common approach to account for them relies on the assumption that the fuel is fully swollen from the beginning of the irradiation time [10]. Radially, the fuel swells and quickly touches the cladding closing the gap that was initially filled by the sodium bond. In this case and following feedback from previous experience, the fuel is assumed to increase its height by 5% while 70% of the sodium bond is

relocated above the fuel rod after being expelled from the fuel-cladding gap. The rest of the sodium bond is infiltrated in the porosities of the metallic fuel.

As a result, Figure 3 (left) shows the core reactivity evolution when applying the selected assumptions for modeling geometrical and composition changes in fuel due to swelling behavior. At the beginning of the irradiation time, the core reactivity increases by around 450 pcm. The two effects are playing different roles since the fuel axial expansion leads to a reactivity decrease while the sodium relocation introduces positive reactivity. A reasonable amount of sodium is expelled above the fuel slug so there will be less sodium in the fuel-clad gap (or in the fuel porosities), hardening the neutron spectrum and leading to a positive reactivity effect. In this case, it can be observed that sodium relocation leads to an overall core reactivity increase. Along the irradiation time, the reactivity difference is maintained, but it further decreases as the irradiation time increases due to reinforced fuel burnup in the case of fuel swelling assumptions.

As reference results, the equilibrium cycle is involved in the study with the aim of assessing the impact of burnup-dependent fuel properties. The ESFR-M core is expected to be operated in a 6-batch mode in a similar way the ESFR-MOX was designed [11]. This means that after a fuel cycle, one fuel batch in both inner and outer regions are discharged and replaced by the fresh fuel subassemblies. The fuel reloading scheme relies on a fuel cycle length of 362 EFPD, which corresponds to 1/6th of the total in-core fuel residence time applied for the once-through calculations. The equilibrium cycle is achieved via the simulation of the 3 full in-core residence periods (i.e., 18 successive fuel cycles).

Concerning the fuel swelling, the reference assumptions are likewise applied for the multi-batch burnup calculations, that fuel is axially expanded by 5% and 70% of sodium bond is relocated above the fuel slug. The calculated cycle-wise core reactivity for the initial 3 full in-core residence periods is shown in Figure 3 (right). As it can be observed, after the first transitional period, the following ones present a very similar cycle-wise reactivity. The core reactivity at the beginning of the equilibrium cycle is around 1250 pcm, with slight variations from cycle to cycle, and a very reduced reactivity swing of around 100 pcm is obtained. The latter feature allows the practical elimination of the CSD withdrawal accident. As a result, there is sufficient end-of-equilibrium (EOEC) reactivity margin, larger than 100 pcm.

In summary, fuel swelling might have a reasonable impact on the neutronic performance of a metallic-fueled SFR. As reference results, the most common assumption to account for this effect has been applied but, as next step, detailed burnup-dependent fuel properties are characterized and subsequently applied to feed the neutronics calculations with the aim of re-evaluating the core performance along the irradiation time.

3. METHODOLOGY

The ESFR-M fuel behavior has been characterized using SAS4A/SASSYS-1 code [12] with boundary conditions from reference Serpent calculations [6]. During irradiation, the fuel rapidly expands while sodium relocation takes more time, which is going to affect the reactor physics calculations. In this section, a dynamic method based on Serpent Monte Carlo code is developed and applied in combination with MFUEL results to track the core performance at every burnup step with updated fuel properties. The ultimate goal of this analysis is to be able to conclude on the validity of the reference modeling assumptions used in Serpent calculations.

The simulation scheme to account for realistic burnup-dependent fuel properties is depicted in Figure 4. It relies on a predictor-corrector approach, where a predictor calculation is firstly performed to characterize the fuel isotopic composition which is applied in a subsequent corrector calculation where fuel dimensions and sodium densities are updated. Fuel isotopic composition is accordingly updated to preserve the total mass after applying the axial expansion. The accuracy of the burnup calculations can be improved by adding more intermediate steps, so that it is highly important having enough burnup steps at the beginning of fresh fuel irradiation to precisely account for the quick fuel axial expansion.

Then, as an example of such workflow, calculations begin with the nominal core at BOL conditions aiming at evaluating the core behavior up to 50 EFPD. In order to improve the accuracy, the irradiation time is divided into 2 steps. At first, a burnup calculation is performed between BOL and 25 EFPD, obtaining the corresponding isotopic composition at the end of that sub-step. The calculated fuel isotopic composition is kept while the fuel dimensions and sodium densities are updated according to MFUEL results, preserving the total fuel mass. Additionally, the level of sodium bond above the fuel slug is updated to allocate the expelled sodium initially located in the fuel-clad gap. Therefore, the core behavior at 25 EFPD is re-evaluated after implementing the described updates, adding another burnup step up to 50 EFPD. At that point, a new isotopic composition is obtained, repeating the procedure and re-evaluating the core performance.

At the beginning of the irradiation, the deviations between the predictor and the corrector calculations will be higher until the fuel expansion stabilizes. In case those deviations are higher than 100 pcm, it is recommended to add another burnup step to avoid the further propagation of deviations.

When dealing with equilibrium cycle calculations, the methodology is separately applied to every batch in the core. That means, fuel assemblies corresponding to different batches will have distinct burnup levels so that fuel properties should be updated accordingly, tracking every batch independently. This also means that different fuel properties are applied to update inner or outer core fuel subassemblies. Furthermore and aiming at adding consistency, when fuel expansion is considered, control rods are also moving upwards to match the top level of the fuel slug.

Figure 4. Simulation flowchart for burnup-dependent neutronics calculation.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Impact on once-through burnup calculations

The first test for the implemented methodology is performed for the ESFR-M once-through burnup calculations from BOL conditions, comparing its outcomes with the reference results presented in Section 2. Figure 5 (left) collects a variety of performed calculations. On the one hand, the reference results are included, both at nominal conditions and applying reference fuel swelling assumptions (i.e., 5% axial expansion and 30% sodium infiltration). As next step, both effects are independently evaluated:

- Firstly, burnup-dependent sodium infiltration (see Figure 5, left, green curve) is analyzed while fuel expansion is kept at 5%. As it can be observed, core reactivity is around 600 pcm lower

with respect to nominal conditions at BOL due to the enhanced leakage effect introduced by the axial fuel expansion. Nonetheless, core reactivity quickly increases as soon as the sodium in fuel-clad gap is being relocated in gas plenum. Due to the positive reactivity effect resulting from the removal of sodium in the fuel region, reactivity reaches the level of nominal results with reference assumptions when sodium relocation stabilizes.

- A similar analysis can be carried out concerning burnup-dependent fuel axial expansion (see Figure 5, left, red curve). Sodium infiltration is kept at 0%, that is nominal conditions, while the methodology described above is applied to characterize how the core reactivity dynamically evolves due to fuel axial expansion. In this case, core reactivity dramatically decreases as the fuel expansion starts. After 100 EFPD, fuel is expanded by around 5% resulting on a reactivity drop of 470 pcm. Fuel expansion slowly increases up to 7.4% at the end of the irradiation time, leading to a more stable reactivity difference with respect to nominal conditions. Then, it can be clearly observed how the two effects considered in this study play reverse roles, leading to a compensating behavior.

Figure 5. On the left: once-through core reactivity as a function of irradiation time and fuel swelling modeling assumptions (burnup-dependent sodium infiltration in green, burnup-dependent fuel axial expansion in red, both effects combined in purple). On the right: cycle-wise core-reactivity from fuel-performance-informed neutronic calculations (both effects are involved).

Finally both effects are considered in a single case. As shown in Figure 5 (left, purple curve), core reactivity slightly decreases after few days of irradiation due to the quick fuel axial expansion, which is not still compensated by the sodium relocation. At 50 EFPD, reactivity decreases by 150 pcm after fuel expands by around 4%. However, the core rapidly recovers the nominal reactivity levels thanks to the sodium bond relocation, which completely stabilizes after 1000 EFPD. From that moment, around 20% of the sodium bond is infiltrated in fuel porosity while the rest 80% is expelled to the gas plenum, obtaining a systematic deviation of around 350 pcm with respect to nominal conditions.

However, when comparing the results obtained with the proposed methodology against those applying reference assumptions, deviations reasonably decrease. In this case, differences are quite large at the beginning of the irradiation time, but they reduce at long-term irradiation times. However, from 1300 EFPD, deviations are systematically larger than 200 pcm. Thus, reliable analyses should consider the burnup-dependent fuel properties to avoid additional uncertainty sources.

4.2. Impact on equilibrium cycle

More interesting than the once-through burnup calculations, the evaluation of the equilibrium cycle using the developed methodology is quite relevant. The EOEC core state is usually applied for extended safety analyses, so its proper characterization is essential before drawing conclusions on the core per-

formance. In this study, the methodology is applied starting from the reference equilibrium cycle and the batches are subsequently updated with burnup-dependent fuel properties. Figure 5 (right) shows how the cycle-wise core reactivity progresses as every batch is replaced.

The high-fidelity calculations start by replacing a single batch (both for IF and OF) and applying burnup-dependent fuel properties from fresh fuel conditions. Then, all the batches are updated along the first iteration, but at different burnup levels. That is, while a certain number of loaded assemblies might have fresh fuel, a different batch will have already swollen fuel. As it can be observed in Figure 5 (right), core reactivity is slowly decreasing as the batches are replaced to track their detailed evolution. At the end of the first iteration, the core reactivity decreases by more than 200 pcm compared to the reference equilibrium cycle. Additionally, the reactivity swing for one cycle is even lower when applying burnup-dependent calculations.

The second iteration aims at providing a well-converged multi-batch operation. Control rods are relocated at this point to match the top of the outer fuel slug, leading to a slight reactivity increase. From now on, all the batches evolve with detailed burnup-dependent properties, showing some oscillations when batches 4 and 5 are replaced. On average, the difference against the reference equilibrium cycle is around 200 pcm, having a systematic reactivity margin of 1000 pcm at end of cycle.

As a follow-up study, it is worthwhile reaching the equilibrium cycle using burnup-dependent properties from BOL conditions rather than progressively modifying each batch. Additionally, the re-evaluation of key safety-related parameters should be carried out using the developed fuel-performance-informed neutronic calculations. Variations with respect to the nominal cases may be expected, given the neutron spectrum differences caused by the dynamic update of the fuel properties.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Metallic fuel properties are subject to noticeable changes as a result of the irradiation in a SFR system. Given that they play a crucial role in the reactor physics performance of the system, a methodology is proposed to quantify their effect on the ESRF-M core behavior. In this study, fuel-performance-informed neutronic calculations are carried out to account for both the fuel axial expansion and the sodium bond relocation. As a result, it has been described how each effect contributes to the core reactivity evolution. While confirming the validity of the nominal simulation assumptions, the developed methodology yielded a maximum reactivity difference of 200 pcm with respect to the reference simulations. Thus, the accurate characterization of burnup-dependent effects can prove useful to reduce the uncertainty in the neutronic simulation inputs. In the future, more effects related to fuel behavior should be properly considered and evaluated. This involves the fission gas release or the clad radial and axial swelling, with the latter potentially impacting the neutronic performance of the system due to the redistribution of inter-assembly sodium.

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